

FISCAL POLICY AS A TOOL FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH: AN IN-DEPTH INSIGHT FROM NIGERIA'S ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

This study empirically examines fiscal policy as a tool for economic growth: an in-depth insight from Nigeria's economy, using an annual time series dataset for the period 2003 to 2023. Secondary data was generated from Central Bank Statistical Bulletin and World Development Indicators (WDI). The study employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model for the analysis of the parameters. The variables studies are economic growth, capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure, tax revenue, crude oil revenue, and domestic debt. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for this study. The descriptive results suggest that all the variables have positive mean. This suggests that none of the series has recorded negative mean over the sample period. The implication of the positive mean is that, all the variables in the model recorded positive average growth rate during the period under review. The inferential analysis began with estimation of unit roots and the results revealed that variables were stationary at different orders of integration. Furthermore, the cointegration test shows that there is an evidence of cointegration among the variables. Based on the cointegration result, this study then moves further and applied error correction mechanism of ARDL approach so as to generate the estimated long-run and short-run results. Based on the estimate this study reveals that there is negative but statistically significant relationship between domestic debt and economic growth. There is positive but statistically significant relationship between capital expenditure and economic growth. There is positive but statistically significant relationship between recurrent expenditure and economic growth. There is positive but statistically significant relationship between tax revenue and economic growth. There is positive but statistically insignificant relationship between crude oil revenue and economic growth. This study recommends the need for government to adopt fiscal mechanism that will encourage increase in revenue through tax and ensure that more of government spending should be channeled to area of economic growth.

Keyword: Gross Domestic Product, crude oil revenue, Tax revenue, Capital expenditure, Recurrent expenditure, and Domestic debt

INTRODUCTION

The impact of fiscal policy on economic growth has continued to generate debate among economists, scholars and policy makers in the recent times. Fiscal policy is the means by which a government adjusts its level of spending in order to monitor and influence a nation's economy. Brons and Nijkamp (1999) reported that Fiscal policy administration through the mechanism of government expenditure plays an important role on economic growth and development. Although reduction in government expenditure may adversely affect the economy, yet excess of government expenditure due to increase in recurrent expenses or unproductive use of the collected tax in the economy creates fiscal deficit. In fact, many economists believe that fiscal deficit is the root cause of every illness in the economy. Thus, fiscal deficit can be harmful to welfare which leads to inefficient allocation of resources and can crowd out the private investment (Adesoji and Joel, 2016).

According to Bogdonov (2010) fiscal policy is that policy framework which refers to the way a government influences an economy through revenue collection and spending. In his view, fiscal policy in any economy is the mechanism through which revenue collected through taxes by the government is manipulated in such a way that the performances of some basic macroeconomic variables such as income distribution, aggregate demand, and resource allocation among others are enhanced (Adesoji & Joel 2016).

Fiscal policy, as a major economic stabilization weapon, is a measure purposely and deliberately taken to regulate and control the volume, cost and availability as well as direction of money in an economy to achieve some specified macroeconomic policy objective and to counteract undesirable trends in the economy. Therefore, it cannot be left to the market forces of demand and supply as well as other instruments of stabilization such as monetary and exchange rate policies (Nathan, 2012).

The Nigerian economy has been faced with numerous obstacles and challenges over the years. Ogbole, Amadi and Essi (2011) pointed out that Nigeria's potential for growth and poverty reduction is yet to be realized. A major constraint has been the appropriate adoption and implementation of macroeconomic policies, especially fiscal and monetary policies. Agu, Okwor and Ugwunta (2014) identified this as a major cause of rising inflation and decline in real incomes. Researchers have also identified some of these challenges as: gross mismanagement and misappropriation of public funds (Ubesie, 2016 in Okemini and Uranta, 2008); corruption and ineffective economic policies (Gbosi, 2008); lack of integration of macroeconomic plans and the absence of harmonization and coordination of fiscal policies (Qnoh, 2007); inappropriate and ineffective policies (Anyanwu, 2007). Also, Amadi and Essi (2006) stressed that imprudent public spending, weak sectoral linkages and other socio-economic challenges constitute the bane of rapid economic growth and development in Nigeria. Undoubtedly, fiscal policy is important to the economy of any country, as government's power to tax, to spend and to borrow' affects the disposable income of citizens and corporations, as well as the general business climate. Hence, this study will try to assess the real impact of fiscal policy, as well as the factors that could limit its effectiveness as a macroeconomic stabilization tool in the Nigerian economy. It is very obvious that a sound fiscal policy measure will translate into achievement of macroeconomic goals for economic growth. This expectation clearly underscores the major motivation for this research. However, this study aims to investigate the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria. The objectives of the study are therefore: (i). To investigate the impact

of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. (ii). To assess the impact of crude oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. (iii). To examine the impact of recurrent expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. (iv). To evaluate the impact of capital expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. (v). To assess the impact of domestic debt on economic growth in Nigeria. The rest of the study is presented as follows: section 2 presents the literature review involving the theoretical underpinning of the study and the review of empirical studies. Section 3 focuses on material and methods which captures the data and model specifications. Section 4 analyses the data and divulges the findings, while sections 5 concludes the paper and highlights the recommendations.

2.1 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Fiscal Policy

Arian (2022) reported that fiscal policy is of great importance in the development of the economy. In Kosovo and other countries, fiscal policy plays a key role in economic growth. The state of affairs and the prudence of fiscal policies are essential for the preservation of macroeconomic stability. Fiscal policy relates to government actions in changing the composition of public revenue and expenditure by managing aggregate demand to maintain a steady economic growth with relatively high employment without creating an inflation and without increasing public debt and a satisfactory balance of payments.

Clinton, et al. (2011) reported that, if a fiscal package is very well designed, then pain only arises if the package suffers from an initial lack of credibility, and the length of the period of pain closely corresponds to the length of the period during which credibility needs to be established. If a fiscal package is designed, the long run gain could be much lower or even non-existent, as higher distortions and/or productivity offset the gains from lower real interest rates (Arian 2022).

2.1.2 Tax Revenue

Taxation is the collection of a share of individual and organization income and wealth by the government under the authority of the law. The Nigerian tax System has undergone significant changes in recent times. The Tax Laws are being reviewed with the aim of repelling obsolete provisions and simplifying the main ones. Under current Nigerian law, tax revenue is enforced by the 3 tiers of Government, which are Federal, State, and Local Government with each having its sphere clearly spelt out in the Taxes and Levies Act, 1998. The whole essence of tax revenue is to generate revenue to advance the welfare of the people of a nation with focus on promoting economic growth and development of a country through the provision of basic amenities for improved public services via proper administrative system, and structures (Okpe, Anastesia, Nwakaego, and Ezeoma 2017).

2.1.3 Concept of Crude Oil Revenue

Oil revenue is the income earned from the sale of crude oil. According to Ogbonna and Appah (2012), oil is the main source of government revenue, accounting for about 90% of total exports, and this approximates to 80% of total government revenues in Nigeria. Ilori and Akinwunmi (2020) noted that oil and gas is the major source of revenue in Nigeria as well as supporting the nation for the future. The authors argued that the budget of Nigeria most vital source of income is from oil revenue. It includes, though is not limited to, revenue from the export of crude oil, petroleum income tax receipts, and revenue from the domestic sale of crude oil (Appah Ebimobowei 2022).

2.1.4 Concept of Recurrent Expenditure

Recurrent expenditure refers to expenditure of recurrent expenses that are less discretionary and are made on ongoing programs or activities. It constitutes of wages and salaries, administration, transfers payment, debt repayment and welfare services (Bailey, 2002). Recurrent expenditure refers to expenditure on purchase of goods and services, wages and salaries, operations as well as current grants and subsidies (usually classified as transfer payments). Recurrent expenditure, excluding transfer payments, is also referred to as government final consumption expenditure. The annual budget spells out the direction of the expected expenditure, as it contains details of the proposed expenditure for each year, though the actual expenditures may differ from the budget figures due, for example, to extra budgetary expenditures or allocations during the course of the fiscal year. Recurrent expenditure may affect economic growth through its effects on people's ability and willingness to work, save and invest. Recurrent expenditure is recurring spending or, in other words, spending on items that are consumed and only last a limited period of time. Recurrent expenditure would include wages and salaries and expenditure on consumables and so on (Omitogun & Ayinla, 2007).

2.1.5 Concept of Capital Expenditure

According to Ag'enor (2007) capital expenditure refers to expenditure that is generally more discretionary and is made on new programmes and activities that are yet to reach their final desired state of completion. It constitutes of investment in such schemes as construction of railways, roadways and communication systems, irrigation and power projects, which raise economic growth both directly and indirectly through encouragement of further private investment. Capital expenditures means the expenditure on infrastructure of which its benefit to the citizens lasts beyond the current year and is enjoyed over a long time period. Such expenditure is of non-recurring nature and results in acquisition of permanent assets. (Omitogun & Ayinla, 2007).

2.1.6 Concept of Domestic Debt

Countries experiencing fiscal deficits, especially the developing ones like Nigeria borrow to improve their economic growth. Ebi & Clement, (2013) reported that Domestic debt is a fundamental tool used by the governments in both developed and less developed countries to finance internal and external gaps. Proper and efficient utilization of the resources in the form of debt may enhance productive capacity and economic growth through development related projects. However, if the debt is not effectively utilized and managed, it creates problems for the economy. Government domestic debt is contracted for various reasons. First, it is used to finance the budget deficit when the government is not able to meet its expenditure commitments using domestically raised revenue and externally sourced grants and borrowing. Second, domestic debt is contracted during implementation of monetary policy through open market operations. Third, debt instruments are important in financial markets development. In order to develop and deepen the financial markets, there is need for a steady supply of a wide range of instruments to be traded (Ahmad, Sheikh, & Tariq, 2012).

2.1.7 Economic Growth

Economic growth can be defined as the sustained increase in a country's productive capacity, and per capita national output or net national product over a while. These increases are the basic causes of economic growth. Fiscal policy is one of the most important tools that have a significant effect on all economic sectors and have a real effect on economic variables like the Gross national product, inflation, unemployment, etc. Taxes can be seen as a fiscal policy, macroeconomic, and internal revenue mobilization tool for the attainment of economic growth. Economic growth can be proxied, using different economic indicators, ranging from Gross National Product (GNP), Gross Domestic

Product (GDP), Human Development Index, and Per Capita Income. But in this study, economic growth was measured with Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and Human Development Index (Salami, 2015).

2.2. Theoretical framework

Solow Growth Model

This study is anchored on the Solow Growth Model. Hence the original Solow (1956) model appeared to be at spread with some of the shortfalls. Secondly, the Keynesians are of the opinion that there is strong linkage between government expenditure and economic growth. In their model, it is indicated that increase in government expenditure (on infrastructures) leads to higher economic growth. In opposition to this view, the neo-classical growth models again argue that government fiscal policy is at variance with the growth of national output. This leads to further argument that government fiscal policy (intervention tool) helps to adjust failure that might arise from the inefficiencies of the market. The seminal work of (Barro R., 1990) opened new ground for the investigation of the impact of fiscal policy (government expenditure) on economic growth. In the same view (Dar Atul A, & Amirhaikhali, S., 2002) indicated that fiscal policy in the endogenous growth model is very relevant in the prediction of future economic growth. Therefore, it is worthy of note that the two interesting aspects of the approach adopted had been underpinned and employed in the literature. In the first place by proposing a role for the human capital investment rate, which gives a link between educational and health expenditure and growth. Secondly which identified constant returns to the two variables (K & L), where K is for capital, L for effective labour. According to Solow production model output Y depends positively on both capital K and labour L. the model is specified as:

$$Y_t = f(K, L) \quad (3.1)$$

Where Y = output, F = is technology being exogenously, while K and L are endogenous factors.

2.3 Empirical Review

Nwankwo, Kalu and Chiekezie (2017) investigate the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria from the period of 1970 to 2014. The data used was sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin of various issues and World Bank Development Indicator (WDI) and the Co-integration and Error Correction (ECM) approaches were utilized in analyzing the data. The result of the unit root test shows that government capital expenditure, oil revenue, gross domestic product and tax revenue are stationary at first difference I(1), while government recurrent expenditure is stationary at levels at levels I(0). The co-integration result shows that there are 3 co integrating equations at 5 per cent level of significance. This shows that there exist a long-run relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth. The estimated ECM has the required negative sign of -0.447 (45%) and lies within the accepted region of less than unity although, government capital and recurrent expenditures at lagged two years was found insignificant and therefore has no impact on economic growth. Based on the findings from the empirical analysis, the study recommends among others, the need for the Nigerian government to invest in productive investment through increase in capital expenditure over and above recurrent expenditure to stimulate economic growth.

3.1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study adopted the ex-post facto research design. The study evaluated the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria. The study used archival data whose manifestations have already

occurred and the researcher cannot manipulate the outcome. The study scope is 2003– 2023 and data were sourced from the statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria 2023.

3.2 Model Specification

The specification of the models for this work will be based on the objective of the study. The model will measure the nexus between fiscal policy and economic growth proxies by real gross domestic product. The study will modify and adopt the model of Nwankwo, Kalu & Chiekiezie (2017). The functional form of the model that will be used in this study is specified as follows:

$$GDP = f(TRV, CORV, REX, CEX, DDB) \dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

Where, GDP= Gross domestic product, TRV = Tax Revenue, CORV = Crude oil revenue, REX= Recurrent expenditure, CEX = capital expenditure, DDB = Domestic Debt, Thus, the above equation can be restated as follows:

$$GDP_t = p_0 + p_1 TRV_t + p_2 CORV_t + p_3 REX_t + p_4 CEX_t + p_5 DDB_t + U_t \dots\dots\dots(3.3)$$

Log - linearizing equation II above, we obtain equation III as follows:

$$\text{Log } GDP_t = p_0 + p_1 \text{Log } TRV_t + p_2 \text{Log } CORV_t + p_3 \text{Log } REX_t + p_4 \text{Log } CEX_t + p_5 \text{Log } DDB_t + U_t \dots\dots\dots(3.4)$$

Where:

GDP = Real Gross Domestic Product (Proxy for economic growth), TXR = Federal Government Tax Revenue, CORV = Federal Government Crude Oil Revenue, REX = Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure, CEX = Federal Government Capital Expenditure, DDB = Federal Government Domestic Debt, P_0 = Y- Intercept term. This gives the mean or average value of GDP when all the explanatory variables included in the model put at zero and p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, p_5 are parameters known as partial regression coefficient or partial slope coefficients (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). The coefficients in the models $p_1 - p_5$ define elasticities of the logged variables. U = the stochastic term or the unexplained variation in GDP. It accounts for the variability in the dependent variable that cannot be explained by the linear effect of all the independent variables in the model, t = the time period Lag (Osuala and Jones, 2014).

4.1 Data Analysis and Discussions

The data used for this study are presented in appendix A attached. These include time series on Gross Domestic Product, crude oil revenue, Tax revenue, Capital expenditure, Recurrent expenditure, and Domestic debt for the periods 2003 to 2023 in Nigeria

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics measure the individual characteristics of the variables used in this study. It shows the mean, median, standard deviation, Jarque-Bera and its probability value (Used to measures normality of the data). The descriptive statistics results for the study are presented in the Table 1 below:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	CEX	REX	CORV	TRV	DD
Mean	34692.62	473.9831	1428.311	2430.350	1039.707	2874.888
Median	23688.28	309.0200	461.6000	1230.850	314.4800	898.2500
Maximum	71387.83	2289.000	6997.390	8878.970	4725.600	14272.64
Minimum	13779.26	4.100000	4.750000	7.250000	2.980000	11.19000
Std. Dev.	20241.02	528.2971	1842.588	2723.421	1351.774	4124.112
Jarque-Bera	4.986798	19.57516	12.02124	4.756112	8.991322	16.88934
Probability	0.082629	0.276156	0.212453	0.092731	0.211157	0.341215
Observations	39	39	39	39	39	39

Source: Researcher's Computation from E-view 9.0 (2022).

Table 4.1 above reveals the individual characteristics of the variables used in the study highlighting their median, mean, maximum and minimum values, standard deviation and Jarque-Bera statistics (normality Test). Gross domestic product (GDP) has a mean value of 34692.62 with maximum value of 71387.83 and minimum value of 13779.26. GDP recorded a standard deviation of 20241.02 which is lower than its mean. This indicates that gross domestic product recorded a slow growth within the period under review. GDP also recorded a Jarque-Bera value of 4.986798 with a probability value of 0.082629 which is within the acceptable threshold indicating that GDP is normally distributed.

Capital expenditure (CEX) and recurrent expenditure (REX) recorded mean values of 473.9831 and 1428.311 with maximum values of 2289 and 6997.390 and minimum values of 4.10 and 4.75 respectively. They recorded standard deviation values of 528.2971 and 1842.588 respectively which are higher than their respective means. This indicates that capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure had a fast growth within the period under review. Capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure also recorded a Jarque-Bera value of 19.57516 and 12.02124 with probability values of 0.276156 and 0.212453 respectively indicating that they are normally distributed.

Crude oil revenue (CORV) and Tax revenue (TRV) recorded mean values of 2430.350 and 1039.707 with maximum values of 8878.970 and 4725.600 and minimum values of 7.25 and 2.98 respectively. They recorded standard deviation values of 2723.421 and 1351.774 respectively which are higher than their respective means. This indicates that they had a fast growth within the period under review. They also recorded a Jarque-Bera value of 4.756112 and 8.991322 with probability values of 0.092731 and 0.211157 respectively indicating that they are normally distributed.

Domestic debt (DD) recorded mean value of 2874.888 with maximum value of 14272.64 and minimum values of 11.19. Domestic debt recorded standard deviation value of 4124 which is higher than the respective mean. This indicates that domestic debt has a fast growth within the period under review. Domestic debt also recorded a Jarque-Bera value of 16.88934 with probability value of 0.341215 indicating that is normally distributed.

4.1.2 Correlation Analysis

Here, the independent variables were tested to see if they are correlated and the result is represented in a matrix form. The assumption of Classical Linear Regression Model (CLRM) is that the independent variables are, in no way, correlated with each other. When this is violated, then there is a problem of multi co-linearity. Since multi co-linearity is a question of degree and not of existence, a matrix

coefficient above 0.8 indicates a high degree of multi co-linearity in the model. The correlation matrix is shown in the table below:

Table 4.2 Correlation Matrix

	GDP	CEX	DD	REX	TRV	CORV
GDP	1.000000	0.785567	0.724732	0.566716	0.664517	0.759215
CEX	0.785567	1.000000	0.772157	0.680543	0.718284	0.778540
DD	0.724732	0.772157	1.000000	0.701234	0.773424	0.672348
REX	0.566716	0.680543	0.701234	1.000000	0.645321	0.353204
TRV	0.664517	0.718284	0.773424	0.645321	1.000000	0.784678
CORV	0.759215	0.778540	0.672348	0.353204	0.784678	1.000000

Sources: Computation from the E-view 9.0

The correlation matrix table 2 above shows that there is no multi co-linearity in the model since there is no matrix value in excess of 0.8. This implies that the model conforms to assumption above.

4.1.2 Unit Root Test

The unit root test results obtained for the current study are contained in Table 3 below:

Table 4.3: Unit Root Test Results

Variables	At Level 1(0)	At First Difference 1(1)	Order of Integration	Alpha Value
Gross Domestic product (LGDP)	-1.472057	-7.808418	1(1)	0.0000
Capital Expenditure (LCEX)	-3.641554	-6.323821	1(I)	0.0000
Recurrent Expenditure (LREX)	-2.885999	-8.209865	1(I)	0.0000
Crude Oil Revenue (LCORV)	-2.440897	-6.171975	1(I)	0.0000
Tax Revenue (LTRV)	-3.094696	-7.583600	1(I)	0.0000
Domestic Debt (LDD)	-0.010136	-4.566296	1(I)	0.0008

Source: Researcher's Compilation E-views 9.0 (2022)

Looking at the unit root test results contained in Table 4.4 above reveals that gross domestic products, capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure, Crude oil revenue, Tax revenue, domestic debt, variables are stationary at first difference. Since the decision rule is to reject stationarity if the ADF statistic is less than the 5 per cent critical value, and accept stationarity when the ADF statistic is greater than the 5 per cent criterion value, the ADF absolute value of each of these variables is greater than the 5 per cent critical value at their first difference but less than 5 per cent critical value in their level form. Therefore, all the variables are all stationary of order I(1) . The implications for these empirical results are that the study's variables are suitable tool of analyzing the error correction mechanism since all the variables used in the model were stationary at first difference.

4.1.3 Co-integration Test

Since the unit root test results show that all the variables are stationary at first difference, we proceeded further to carry out the co-integration test.

Table 4.4: Johansen Multivariate Co-integration Test
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
		656.056		
None *	0.994519		239.2354	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.977175	463.4204	197.3709	0.0001
At most 2 *	0.936353	323.5640	159.5297	0.0000
At most 3 *	0.843435	221.6508	125.6154	0.0000
At most 4 *	0.807684	153.0422	95.75366	0.0000
At most 5 *	0.638704	92.04341	69.81889	0.0003

Source: Author's computation using Eview 9, (2022)

From the table 4.4, we reject the null hypothesis of no long run relationship among the variables given that the value of Trace statistics (656.056) at None, is greater than its critical value (239.2354). The same conclusion can be said for At most 1 to At most 5. In effect, the alternative hypothesis which concludes that there was a long run relationship among the variables is accepted. This result is also corroborated by their respective probabilities values (0.0000, 0.0001, 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000 and 0.0003) all of which are under the 5% level of significance, further validating the existence of a long run relationship among the variables under consideration. Based on the result in table 4, there are five cointegrated variables, revealing cointegration among the variables in at least five equations and thus we conclude the existence of a positive and significant long run relationship between economic growth (GDP) and the explanatory variables at 5% level of significance within the study period.

4.1.4 Results of the Diagnostic Tests

Table 4.5. Diagnostic test

Serial Correlation Test			
F-statistic	0.765550	Prob. Value	0.3733
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.470634	Prob. Value	0.8374
Normality Test			
F-Statistics	0.3992	Prob. Value	0.8270

To ensure the reliability of the estimated results, the study conducted post-estimation tests so as to identify the fitness or otherwise of the results. The tests were carried out using autocorrelation, heteroskedasticity and normality tests and the results is tabulated in Table 4.5. From the tests, the results show that the model is reliable and useful in policy making. This is because the probability values of all the tests are not statistically significant even at 10% level. This also explains the absence of serial correlation, heteroskedasticity and the model is normally distributed. 4.6 Error Correction Mechanism (ECM)

The error correction mechanism result is presented in table 6 below:

Table 4.6: Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.987024	0.362051	13.77436	0.0000
LDD	-0.230964	0.067817	-3.632577	0.0001
LCEX	0.167343	0.044869	3.435782	0.0003
LREX	0.238065	0.110818	2.847231	0.0041
LTRV	0.261702	0.064668	3.467345	0.0002
LCORV	0.064342	0.055403	0.806322	0.6372
ECM(-1)	-0.487212	0.121871	-2.321238	0.0271
Mean dependent var				
R-squared	0.992110			3.824044
Adjusted R-squared	0.984743	S.D. dependent var		0.224308
S.E. of regression	0.093904	Akaike info criterion		-
				1.655894
Sum squared resid	0.238084	Schwarz criterion		-
				1.181856
Log likelihood	42.46198	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-
				1.487235
F-statistic	12.41185	Durbin-Watson stat		1.652011
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher's computations using E-view 9.0 (2022)

4.1.5 Domestic Debt

The value of the coefficient of domestic debt is -0.230964 with a t-statistic value of -3.632577 and a probability value of 0.0001. The implications for these empirical findings are that domestic debt has a negative but significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria at 1 per cent level during the period covered by the study.

4.1.6 Capital Expenditure:

The value of the coefficient of capital expenditure is 0.167343 with a t-statistics value of 3.435782 and a probability value of 0.0003. This empirical finding implies that capital expenditure had a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria at 1 per cent level during the study period.

4.1.7 Recurrent Expenditure:

The value of the coefficient of recurrent expenditure is 0.238065 with a t-statistics value of 2.847231 and a probability value of 0.0041. This empirical finding implies that recurrent expenditure has a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria also at 1 per cent level during the study period.

4.1.8 Tax Revenue

The value of the coefficient of Tax revenue is 0.261702 with a t-statistic value of 3.467345 and a probability value of 0.0002. These empirical findings imply that tax revenue has a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria at 1 per cent level during the study period.

4.1.9 Crude Oil Revenue

The value of the coefficient of crude oil revenue is 0.064342 with a t-statistic value of 0.806322 and a probability value of 0.6372. These empirical findings show that crude oil revenue has a positive relationship with economic growth in Nigeria at an insignificant level during the study period covered.

4.1.10 Error Correction Mechanism

The value of the coefficient of error correction mechanism is (ECM-1) is -0.487212 .

Consequently, the error correction term has the needed sign, negative, less than one and statistically significant at 1%. This is confirming the evidence of long run relations among the series. The result also shows that, in case of any distortion in the economy, the error correction term will correct itself from the disequilibrium toward the equilibrium approximately 48 per cent and this is impressive.

4.8.7 (R^2)

The R^2 0.99 shows that the explanatory variables have explained about 99% of the total variations in the dependent variable which is good fit.

4.8.8 F-statistics

The F-statistic result of 12.41185 with probability value of 0.0000 shows that these explanatory variables are jointly significant in explaining the variation in the dependent variable which is a good fit.

4.8.9 Durbin-Watson (DW) Statistics

The Durbin Watson is 1.652011 which shows that there is presence of serial correlation which implies that some other factors affecting economic growth in Nigeria are omitted in the model.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between Tax Revenue and Economic Growth in Nigeria.

Looking at the t statistics of 3.467345 and probability value 0.0002 is statistically significant, therefore we are to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, and concluded that tax revenue has influence on economic growth in Nigeria.

4.2.2 Test of Hypotheses Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between crude oil revenue and economic growth in Nigerian. From the estimated result it was observed that the t statistics 0.806322 and probability value of 0.6372 is statistically insignificant, therefore we are to accept the null hypotheses and reject the alternative hypotheses and concluded that crude oil revenue has no influence on economic growth in Nigeria.

4.2.3 Test of Hypotheses Three

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between recurrent expenditure and economic growth in Nigerian.

However, from the estimated result observed that the t statistics 2.847231 and probability value of 0.0041 is statistically significant. Therefore, we are to reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses. The conclusion here is that recurrent expenditure has influence on economic growth in Nigeria.

4.2.4 Test of Hypotheses Four

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between capital expenditure and economic growth in Nigerian.

Result from the study analysis revealed that the t statistics 3.435782 and the probability value of 0.0003 is strong and statistically significant. Therefore, we are to reject the null hypotheses, by rejecting the null hypotheses we have to accept alternative hypotheses and concluded that capital expenditure has influence on economic growth in Nigeria.

4.2.5 Test of Hypotheses Five

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between domestic debt and economic growth in Nigerian. Result from the study analysis revealed that the t statistics -3.632577 and the probability value of 0.0001 is also strong and statistically significant. Therefore, we are to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and concluded that domestic debt has influence on economic growth in Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

This section discusses the findings of this study in relation to the findings of the literature reviewed in chapter two and explains the extent to which the findings are similar or otherwise with the studies reviewed.

From the result, this study revealed that there is positive and significant relationship between capital expenditure and economic growth. This is contrary with work of Munongo (2012) who reveals that capital expenditure by government has a negative effect and a long-run relationship with economic growth as confirmed by the cointegration test. The findings are also in line with the work of Ogbole, Amadi and Essi (2011), who revealed that there exists causal relationship between fiscal policy and GDP in Nigeria in the period under review. Which is also corresponds with the work of Nathan (2012) which confirmed that fiscal policies have significant influence on the output of the Nigerian economy.

The result shows that recurrent expenditure has positive and significant impact on economic growth. This is confirmed with findings of Osuala and Jones (2014), who revealed that government recurrent has significant and positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study is also in line with the work of Iheanacho (2016), who revealed a positive short-run relationship between recurrent expenditure and economic growth.

The study revealed that government domestic debt has negative and significant effect on economic growth. The finding is contrary to the finding of Osuala and Jones (2014), who found that government total debts have no significant impact on real GDP.

The study also revealed that government tax revenue has positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. This is in line with the work of Dibia & Onwuchekwa (2019), who found that petroleum profit tax (PPT) and company income tax (CIT) show positive and significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) in Nigeria. The study is also confirmed with the work of Festus, Appolos and Olaleken (2020), who found that non-oil taxes (custom and excise duties, capital gain tax, company income tax, tertiary education tax and value added tax) have significant effect on economic growth. The study contradicts with the work of Anthony, Edeh & Wilfred (2015), who found that direct income tax is inversely related and statistically significant in determining economic growth in the long run.

5.1 Conclusions

Based on the above findings, the study therefore concluded that tax revenue, capital expenditure, and recurrent expenditure have a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. But crude oil revenue has a positive but insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. The study finally concludes that Domestic debt has a negative but significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

5.2 Recommendations

In line with findings, this study recommends the following:

- i. That government should adopt fiscal mechanism that will encourage increase in revenue through tax and ensure that more of government spending should be channeled to areas such as economic and social that help to grow the economy given their positive and significant effect on the growth of the economy of Nigeria.
- ii. That government must strive to sustain the current unflinching commitment towards improving tax revenue, ensure Tertiary Education Tax collected translates into real development and also ensure efficient utilization of tax payers' money to boost tax revenue collection which will then lead to economic growth and development.
- iii. That to maintain a stable economic growth in Nigeria, the central bank need to inject more money into the economy and the government should use her revenue and expenditure at full optimization.
- iv. That the government should ensure that the share of recurrent expenditure in total expenditures is kept within a reasonable proportion by blocking all leakages and wastages in public financing in the country.

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APPENDIX A

DATA FOR THE ANALYSIS

YEARS	GDP	TRV	CORV	REX	CEX	DDB
2003	31709.5	500.82	2074.28	984.3	241.69	4478.33
2004	35020.6	565.7	3354.8	1110.64	351.25	4890.27
2005	37475	785.1	4762.4	1321.23	519.47	2695.07
2006	39995.5	677.54	5287.57	1390.1	552.39	451.46
2007	42922.4	1264.6	4462.91	1589.27	759.28	438.89
2008	46012.5	1336	6530.6	2117.36	960.89	523.25
2009	49856.1	1652.65	3191.94	2127.97	1152.8	590.44
2010	54612.3	1907.58	5396.09	3109.44	883.87	689.84
2011	57511	2237.88	8878.97	3314.51	918.55	896.85
2012	59929.9	2628.78	8025.97	3325.16	874.7	1026.9
2013	63218.7	2950.56	6809.23	3214.95	1108.39	1387.33
2014	67218.7	3275.03	6793.82	3426.94	783.12	1631.5
2015	69023.9	3082.41	3830.1	3831.95	818.35	2111.51
2016	67931.2	2922.5	2693.9	4160.11	653.61	3478.91
2017	68491	3335.2	4109.8	4779.99	1242.3	5787.51
2018	69810	4006	5545.8	5675.2	1682.1	7759.2
2019	71387.8	4725.6	5536.66	6997.39	2289	9022.42
2020	70835.2	4689.6	6509.23	5787.59	2547.3	8211.47
2021	72439.5	4811.2	5196.09	6344.4	2201.5	8998.5
2022	79354.5	5220.1	6282.22	6923.3	2245.6	9437.2
2023	83217.8	6110.8	6752.72	7921.9	2867.4	9728.39

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2022.